

Implementation of Maritime Transport Mitigation Measures according to their Marginal Abatement Costs and their Mitigation Potentials

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Abstract

The International Maritime Organization (IMO) has set a target to reduce GHG emissions from shipping by 50% by 2050 compared to 2008. Some studies focused on negative cost mitigation measures to achieve this goal, while it is almost a consensus that alternative maritime fuels with low or zero direct GHG emissions are needed. This article gathered data from implementation, marginal abatement costs (MAC) and mitigation potentials of 22 mitigation measures, to assess their implementation according to their MAC and GHG abatement potentials. Findings showed that negative MAC measures are more implemented than positive MAC measures, and that negative MAC measures have at least a 25% of implementation rate, with one exception, and for some, this exceeds 50%. Among the measures with high mitigation potential, only the zero-emission fuels measure has a low implementation rate, although it is crucial to reach IMO's target. Hence, studies that analyze emission reduction scenarios should consider the implementation rate since there are still opportunities to overcome market barriers to negative MAC measures, not yet fully implemented, and zero-emission fuel measures should be further promoted due to their crucial role in mitigating emissions.

Keywords

International Maritime transport, Greenhouse gases, Marginal Abatement Cost, Mitigation Potential

1. Introduction

Maritime transport accounts for approximately 3% of global CO₂ emissions (MEPC 75, 2020; SMITH et al., 2014). Balcombe et al. (2019) present an analogy between CO₂ emissions from maritime transport and emissions by country, in which maritime transport would be the sixth largest emitter in the world, ahead of Brazil and Germany. The Paris Agreement, held at the 2015 United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP21), recognizes the need for an effective response to the urgent threat of climate change. The agreement committed to keep the

1 increase in the global average temperature below 2°C — with efforts to limit it to 1.5°C —
 2 compared to pre-industrial levels. Although maritime transport does not have a nationality and
 3 is not within the agreement, the International Maritime Organization (IMO), a UN body that
 4 regulates actions in the maritime sector, recognizes the need to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG)
 5 emissions by 50% by 2050, compared to 2008, in a manner consistent with the goals of the a
 6 agreement as mentioned above (MEPC 72, 2018). To understand the challenge for the maritime
 7 transport sector in achieving this goal, the emission of ships has been studied by many authors
 8 (CORBETT and KOEHLER, 2003; EYRING et al., 2005; SMITH et al., 2014; LINDSTAD et
 9 al., 2015; OLMER et al., 2017; MEPC 75, 2020). In order to analyze how these emissions
 10 evolved, Figure 1 presents data from Buahug et al. (2009), Smith et al. (2014) and MEPC 75
 11 (2020).

Figure 1 History of CO₂ and CO_{2eq} Emissions in International Maritime Transport (data from the 2nd study by IMO (BUHAUG et al., 2009) are in CO₂ and the others in CO_{2eq})

From 1990 to 2008, there was an increase in GHG emissions accompanied by the growth of the maritime transport market (MEPC 75, 2020). Between 2007 and 2012 there was a drop in emissions, and between 2012 and 2018 there was a period of stability with an increase in emissions at the end. However, Eskeland and Lindstad (2016) show that global sea freight work grew from 1990 to 2012. To explain this drop in emissions and increase in the freight market, Lindstad et al. (2015) and Olmer et al. (2017), in addition to the 4th IMO Study (MEPC 75, 2020), observe a trend of efficiency gains in the maritime sector between 2008 and 2012,

1 and this trend remained until 2018 - but with less intensity than in the previous period (MEPC
2 75, 2020). Lindstad et al. (2015), Olmer et al. (2017) and MEPC 75 (2020) consider that two
3 measures, a technological one and an operational one, were necessary for this increase in
4 efficiency: the increase in the size of the ships (included in the hull shape measurement in this
5 article) and the speed reduction after 2008 (slow steaming).
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9 The implementation of greenhouse gases (GHG) emission mitigation measures was
10 encouraged from 2011 onwards with the adoption of IMO policies defining the Energy
11 Efficiency Design Index (EEDI), a mandatory measure for new ships, and the Ship Energy
12 Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP), which voluntarily encourages ship owners in operation
13 to use the Energy Efficiency Operational Indicator (EEOI)¹.
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18 Some authors have analyzed the mitigation measures and showed that some of them
19 result in negative Marginal Abatement Costs (MAC), that is, they provide economic returns if
20 implemented by ship operators, in addition to reducing emissions (BUHAUG et al., 2009;
21 EIDE et al., 2009; EIDE et al., 2011; ICCT, 2011; FABER et al., 2011; LINDSTAD et al.,
22 2015; MEPC 75, 2020). However, the literature review by Rehmatulla and Smith (2020)
23 reports that there are few studies on the implementation of mitigation measures in the maritime
24 sector. In addition, Rehmatulla et al. (2017b) criticize the data provided by the IMO to assess
25 the technologies implemented to reduce EEDI. The authors argue that the data do not show the
26 innovations nor the technologies that have been implemented, thus making it difficult to assess
27 which measures have shown significant results in reducing emissions.
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36 The potential of mitigation measures to achieve the IMO goals of reducing emissions
37 by 50% (values close to 500 Mt of CO_{2eq}) by 2050 has been studied by several authors (EIDE
38 et al., 2016; BOUMAN et al., 2017; BALCOMBE et al., 2019; SCHWARTZ et al., 2020;
39 MEPC 75, 2020; CASSERES et al., 2021a). Among these authors, there is a debate about the
40 feasibility of achieving these reductions using only negative MAC measures or using zero-
41 emission fuel measures², which have a high MAC value. EIDE et al. (2011) stated in 2011 that
42 there is no “silver bullet”, and that the solution for mitigation is the use of several measures in
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52 ¹The Carbon Intensity Index (*Energy Efficiency Operational Indicator - EEOI*) of the international maritime
53 transport sector, showed a reduction of 29%, compared to 2008 (MEPC 75, 2020). Different companies have
54 reported the EEOI in their annual reports (eg, see, *EURONAV, 2020; TEEKAY GROUP, 2021*)
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56 ² It is worth stressing that zero or low GHG emission fuels in the reports usually account for only direct emissions
57 derived from fuel combustion in the ship, meaning that life-cycle emissions are not considered. The full-cycle
58 emissions from some alternative fuels might be relevant, however, as shown by Casseres et al. (2021b).
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1 the fleet. The study by Lloyds and Umas (2017) reinforces this direction but points to zero
2 emission fuels.
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5 “Fossil fuels provide society in general, as well as shipping, with a high-
6 density and low-cost energy source that is comparatively easy to store, handle
7 and transport. We have had decades to optimize the design, maintenance and
8 operation of the shipping system to suit the fossil ‘paradigm’. But the world
9 is changing. It is, therefore, unsurprising that when looking for a non-fossil,
10 zero-emission and sustainable energy source, as we must urgently now do,
11 it’s difficult to see an obvious ‘silver bullet’.” (LLOYDS and UMAS, 2017).
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19 Bouman et al. (2017), in a compilation of 14 studies on emission estimates, despite
20 finding few scenarios in which estimate reductions were below 500 Mt of CO₂ by 2050,
21 concluded that it would be possible to reach the goals of the agreement with the combination
22 of only 7 measures that do not include zero-emission fuels, when analyzing 22 mitigation
23 measures. Schwartz et al. (2020) write an article investigating the possibilities of reducing
24 emissions cost-effectively, and present a result for general cargo ships, concluding that a 50%
25 reduction could be achieved costlessly and that 70% of reduction could be achieved without
26 the inclusion of zero emission fuels. The 4th IMO study (MEPC 75, 2020) identified that
27 negative MAC measures would have only an 18% reduction potential and that, in order to reach
28 the agreement's goals, the use of zero-emission fuels would be necessary. Eide et al. (2016)
29 present a scenario with the application of 17 GHG emission mitigation measures. However, to
30 achieve a 40% reduction, the authors needed to include zero emission fuels. Balcombe et al.
31 (2019) make an analysis that includes five mitigation measures and zero emission fuels, thus
32 achieving the goals of the IMO. Casseres et al. (2021a), in an analysis of 5 global scenarios for
33 the energy system and soil use, indicate that international maritime transport would only reach
34 the IMO target with the use of zero emission fuels. Therefore, according to these authors,
35 energy efficiency measures on ships would not be sufficient, even if relevant.
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50 In sum, while most authors understand that it is only possible to meet IMO’s target with
51 the use of zero emission fuels, other authors argue that it would be possible to reach the goal
52 with a set of low-cost mitigation measures, and few authors find that it is possible only with
53 negative MAC measures. However, in many of these studies, it was not evident whether the
54 implementation rate of operational and technological measures was considered to analyze their
55 potential for mitigating GHG. This rate interferes with the fleet's global mitigation capacity,
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1 since it is not possible to consider that part of the fleet will implement a measure that has
2 already been installed. This would configure an overestimated reduction potential.

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4 Thus, this study aims to evaluate the implementation of mitigation measures,
5 correlating their current implementation with their marginal abatement cost (MAC) values and
6 mitigation potentials. By doing that, this study also tests the hypothesis that mitigation
7 measures with the lowest MAC have been more implemented, even if they are not the measures
8 with the greatest abatement potential; or, in other words, that mitigation measures have been
9 applied more like a “win-win” strategy, aimed at reducing costs, than precisely because of their
10 abatement potential.
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13 The methodology used in this article was based on secondary data analyses of related
14 studies, carrying out a data survey of mitigation potentials, MACs and implementation rates.
15 Then, the results of the analyses were systematized to contribute to formulating policies to
16 reach IMO’s target, also considering that the EEDI receives a lot of criticism (LISTER et al.,
17 2015; HAUN, 2017), as this indicator is insufficient to lead to the reduction of emissions
18 defined in the resolution of IMO MEPC 72(2018) (WANG and LUTSEY, 2013; EIDE et al.,
19 2016, CASSERES et al., 2021a).
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22 The article is organized into four sections, besides this introduction. The next one
23 systematizes the literature review, discussing the resolutions associated with reducing
24 greenhouse gases, dealing with how the MACs are calculated and presenting the barriers to the
25 implementation of mitigation measures. Then, the methodology applied in this study is
26 presented. The fourth section presents the results of the analysis, focusing on assessing the
27 implementation rates, MACs and mitigation potentials of abatement measures. Finally, the
28 concluding remarks of the paper highlights the main messages of the study and its implications
29 to mitigation policies.
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31 **2. Literature Review**

32 **2.1. Resolutions Associated with the Reduction of Greenhouse Gases in International 33 Maritime Transport**

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35 Lindstad et al. (2015) summarize the most important IMO reports and resolutions
36 related to GHG emissions derived from international shipping. In 2000, the IMO issues the first
37 GHG study; in 2003, the IMO Assembly forced its Marine Environment Protection Committee
38 (MEPC) to develop mechanisms to reduce GHG; MPEC 55 agreed on a work plan to develop
39 operational and market methods and techniques for GHG reduction and update the first study;
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the 59th session of the MEPC culminated in the presentation of the second IMO study in 2009 about GHG and the approval of the principles of the Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) and the Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP); in 2011, at the 62nd session of the MEPC, both were adopted as part of MARPOL, the EEDI came into operation in 2013 and in 2015 the Paris Agreement was signed. In 2016, the IMO again formulated actions for GHG, and in MEPC 70 (2016): the collection of fuel oil consumption data for 5000 AB ships was defined as mandatory from 2019 onwards. Then, those data started to support the formulation of short, medium and long term policies to reduce GHG. Finally, at MEPC 72 in 2018, the IMO approved an initial strategy to reduce GHG emissions, including reducing and eliminating GHG emissions as quickly as possible, still in this century. Within this strategy, which constitutes an important milestone in the postulations of this body, the following stands out: diminishing the carbon intensity of ships through other phases of the EEDI; reducing emissions per ton transported by 40% by 2030, and by 70% by 2050 (both based on 2008); reach peak emissions as quickly as possible and reduce total annual emissions by 50% by 2050, consistent with the Paris agreement target (IMO, 2019).

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Then, in 2019, at MEPC 74, progress was made in the action program of IMO's initial strategy for GHG reduction, with the approval of amendments to annex VI to take effect from MEPC 75, of April 2020. There was also a reinforcement of the EEDI policy, particularly the anticipation of phase 3 from 2025 to 2022, relating to various types of ships, including containers, gas carriers and general cargo. There was also an increase in the percentage reduction rate of phase 3 EEDI for container carriers above 200,000 dwt, rising from 30% to 50%. In addition, the 4th IMO study was approved, which began at MEPC 74 and will be delivered at MEPC 76, with an available preview at MEPC 75, discussed in this article. The resolution of MEPC.323 (74), which encourages Member States to create cooperation between the port and maritime sectors to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, proposes *onshore* supplying preference to renewable sources (*cold ironing*), the provision of supply of low emission fuel and zero emission fuels, and facilitating *just-in-time* arrivals at ports. A debate on policies to reduce methane leakage and concrete policies to encourage low emission fuel and zero emission fuel was also approved for the meetings of the intersectoral committee in March 2020 (IMO, 2019).

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Despite the gain from these declarations of intent, the IMO text raises a concern with the lack of concrete actions, illustrating how challenging is to speed up actions to curb emissions. Mander (2017) states that international maritime transport is a socio-technical system, therefore composed of elements such as users' interests, cultural behaviors,

1 technologies and policies. These aspects are maintained by a diverse group of actors.
2 Sociotechnical systems are marked by stability and inertia, leading the most common changes
3 to be incremental since radical changes must break with the common practices and with
4 consolidated technologies. However, for the sector to meet the demands of the Paris
5 Agreement, a broad shift from the fossil fuel system to a new low-carbon system is needed.
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9 The EEDI is an emission control instrument. However, to reach its reduction goal, it
10 does not define a path; on the contrary, it defines a goal to be achieved, leaving the market to
11 search for optimal solutions. This path may seem interesting because, given the immaturity of
12 some technologies and the few experiments in the application of mitigation technology on large
13 ships, it can lead operators to seek and test different solutions, creating conditions for their
14 development (WAN et al., 2018; HALF et al., 2019). On the other hand, at the same time, this
15 policy exempts the IMO from the responsibility of defining the winning strategy and getting
16 involved in this complex solution. According to Wan et al. (2018), this policy has affected the
17 objective of achieving significant CO₂ reductions, as it does not seem that the market is willing
18 to take risks experimenting with new technologies with radical changes, instead of maintaining
19 the tendency to inertia and marginal gains. In addition, Rehmatulla et al. (2017b) criticize the
20 data provided by the IMO to assess the technologies implemented to reduce EEDI. The data do
21 not show the innovations, or the technologies that have been implemented, thus making it
22 difficult to assess which measures have shown significant results, therefore hindering the
23 formulation of new policies or even the exchange of information that generate confidence for
24 investments in the sector (REHMATULLA et al., 2017b).
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38 In sum, one of the main current policy instruments to control emissions is the EEDI,
39 and mitigation studies indicate that this action alone will not achieve IMO's 50% reduction goal
40 by 2050 (WANG and LUTSEY, 2013; EIDE et al., 2016, CASSERES, 2021a). Therefore, the
41 review of policy instruments for reducing greenhouse gas emissions from international
42 maritime transport is necessary. In addition to that, to evaluate mitigating pathways, it is
43 necessary to observe how the composition of GHG abatement costs takes place.
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50 **2.2. Marginal Abatement Cost Curves (MACC) of International Maritime Transport** 51 **GHG Emissions** 52

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54 “Marginal Abatement Cost Curves (MACC) are a staple element of policy
55 discussions where there is a need to illustrate the incremental contributions of
56 parts to a whole. In this instance, they provide a simple and elegant way to
57 illustrate greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reductions from design standards,
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1 retrofit technologies, and operational measures that improve ship energy
2 efficiency relative to their costs” (ICCT, 2011).
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5 The MEPC 62 report (2011) defines the marginal abatement cost (MAC) as the quotient
6 between the total costs of implementing a mitigation measure and its effects (reduction of CO₂
7 emissions performed by that same measure). The total installation costs may include an initial
8 cost and operating costs for using, maintaining and immobilizing the boat to install the
9 mitigation measure. Operating costs also include the fuel cost, which is always negative,
10 referring to the reductions in consumption made by each mitigation measure. These costs are
11 converted to annual values, and for this a discount rate is used, as well as the measurement of
12 mitigated CO₂ referring to one year of service. Equation 1, is presented below, taken from
13 MEPC 62 (2011), which determines the MAC for each mitigation measure j:
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$$24 \quad \text{MAC} = \frac{k_j + S_j - E_j + \sum O_j}{25 \quad \alpha_j \times C_f \times F} \quad (1)$$

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29 Where: k_j - the annual capital cost of installing the mitigation measure (total cost divided
30 by the ship's lifetime), corrected by the discount rate; S_j - the annual operating costs of
31 the mitigation measure; E_j - the annual amount that is no longer spent on fuel due to the
32 implementation of the measure; O_j - opportunity costs lost due to time not operating to
33 install the technology; α_j - the technology's mitigation potential in percentage; C_f - the
34 fuel's carbon emission factor; F - the annual fuel consumption before installation.
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42 The negative element in equation 1 refers to fuel cost and allows MAC to have a
43 negative value. When this occurs, the ship operator has an economic incentive to use these
44 mitigation measures, as in addition to reducing their emissions, it financially saves with the
45 installation of the measure (PSARAFTIS, 2012).
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49 After defining a MAC value for each mitigation measure, it is worth drawing the
50 Marginal Abatement Cost Curves (MACCs). The MACCs gather several mitigation measures
51 presented in ascending order of MAC value on the y axis, whereas on the x axis the mitigation
52 potential of each measure is presented, which will be expressed as a percentage of mitigation
53 in relation to a given future year or in the value per ton of mitigated CO₂, also for a given year,
54 and always for a specific fleet. Therefore, the x axis is the sum of the mitigated CO₂ of all ships
55 that compose the fleet. This value is composed of the accumulated emissions year by year. This
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curve can be displayed aggregating the data by mitigation measure, according to the average value for the MAC, as in Eide et al. (2011); or not detailing the reduction potential of each measure, as in MEPC 62 (2011) (FABER et al., 2011).

To build the MACC it is necessary to evaluate the number of measures installed on ships each year, given that the technologies are not all implemented at the same time - some measures need to be installed on new ships, others need the already operational ship to be *in the dry* (docked). Therefore, to produce this data, it is necessary to define a fleet, and assess how many ships it has and how many belong to each class (oil tankers, container carriers, etc.), the sizes of the ships, the current age of the ships that compose the fleet, the service life of the ship and the fleet expected for each class of ship in the next year, considering an increase or decrease in the maritime transport market. Thus, for each year, it is necessary to analyze whether any ship was removed from the fleet at the end of its service life, as well as how many entered the fleet, and each new ship inserted will require a mitigation measure to be installed. Retrofit installations are usually performed in the *dry* docking year, which is normally carried out every five years. It is also important not to add conflicting measures in the same ship, that is, they cannot be installed together, as is the case of measures for zero emission fuels and low emission fuels. In addition, some measures cannot be installed on all types of ships or on all sizes; therefore, fleet variation must be analyzed in a specific way containing age, type and size of the ship. The service life of a ship is usually thirty years (EIDE et al., 2011; FABER et al., 2011; ICCT, 2011). These curves can be generated for each type of ship, due to the heterogeneity of the fleet, and can be generated as the sum of the world fleet, covering all types of ships as done in this article.

Yuan et al. (2016) consider the characteristics and uncertainties of MACCs, and propose the inclusion of a curve that demonstrates the uncertainties and probabilities of the mitigation potential in their designs. The 4th IMO study also includes a percentage of installation of mitigation measures to draw the curves. Faber et al. (2011) comment that the MACCs can include learning effects that reduce the MAC, or that increase the mitigation potential over the years. The aforementioned study also comments that the speed reduction mitigation measure may have a MAC of -210USD/tCO₂ for one type and size of vessel and 1500USD/tCO₂ for another type and size of the vessel, using the average value of -60USD/tCO₂ (FABER et al., 2011), which illustrates an important feature when considering the average as in this article.

In recent years, many MACCs have been published with different results for MAC values. Some criterion can lead to these differences: definition of the emissions baseline,

1 difference in which mitigation measures were used in the analysis, differences in costs used, in
2 potentials adopted, in the size and type of the studied fleet, differences in fuel prices, in the
3 discount rate, in the fleet renewal rate, as well as in the efficiency of the current fleet (FABER,
4 et al., 2011).
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7 The proper definition and understanding MACs contribute to GHG mitigation policy
8 formulation for the sector. According to Psaraftis (2012), positive MAC measures require
9 interventions to be implemented. However, the author indicates that negative MAC
10 technologies do not require regulation, as they have a “win-win” proposition for the operator.
11 Thence, this author does not consider the market barriers that hinder the implementation of
12 negative MAC measures, and it is worth noting them to contribute to the understanding of the
13 difficulties in implementing mitigation measures.
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21 **2.3. Barriers to the Implementation of Mitigation Measures**

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23 Rehmatulla and Smith (2015a) and Rehmatulla et al. (2017a) discuss which barriers
24 stand in the way of the implementation of measures with negative MACs in maritime transport.
25 They divided them into market failures and non-market failures. To understand the differences
26 between them, the authors assume that the market will always make a “rational” choice for
27 profit optimization. A “non-rational” choice would be a market failure. Analyzing four non-
28 market failures, the article defines heterogeneity, risk, hidden costs and access and costs of
29 capital. **Heterogeneity** indicates that a mitigation measure may or may not be feasible
30 depending on the ship's class, size, etc. The **risk** is related to the variation of costs according
31 to fuel prices, which are volatile, as shown by Lindstad et al. (2015) — which present the
32 MACCs for three fuel price ranges. In addition, another relevant point for risk analysis is the
33 variation in the technological maturity of mitigation measures, with greater risk for measures
34 with low maturity. **Hidden costs** are due to simplifications in cost modeling, as many items do
35 not include, for example, maintenance costs, vessel life variables, installation contract cost, and
36 retrofit implementation costs, leading to wrong MAC values. **Access and costs of capital,**
37 being restricted, means that operators do not adopt long-term measures of return.
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51 The second group of barriers refers to market failures, which occur when resource
52 allocation optimization principles are violated. Two main reasons stand out: lack of information
53 and split costs or contract problems. **Lack of Information**, which is a factor that leads to non-
54 rational use of resources, can be motivated by imprecision, a gap or lack of access to
55 information about a certain mitigation measure. **Split costs or contract problems** refer to the
56 fact that, although the installation of a technology is profitable over the service life of the ship,
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1 depending on the form of the contract, the fuel cost may be borne by the charterer, but the
2 capital investment cost is imputed to the owner (time charter) — which can lead to different
3 perspectives, causing the technological measure not to be installed. Nevertheless, a market
4 research by Rehmatulla and Smith (2020) contradicted this hypothesis. One possible
5 explanation is the appreciation of the charter contract, due to the greater demand for high-
6 efficiency ships. Some of the barriers presented in this subsection will be reviewed further in
7 this paper to explain the relationship between implementation and MACs.
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13 **3. Methodology**

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16 The methodological procedure of this study is depicted in the flowchart of Figure 2.
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Figure 2 - Flowchart of the article's methodology. (Rectangles refer to processes performed by the authors; diamond to decisions; super ellipses to data compilations and analyses; hexagons to test applied according to the objective of the work; Notes in yellow rectangles refer to the data source used in data collection)

The first step to correlate the implementation of mitigation measures by the maritime sector with their MAC values and their mitigation potentials was to select 22 mitigation measures that have been being evaluated by scientific studies - see Table 1.

Table 1 Studies from where the data was taken to compose the results of the next chapter.

Academic Studies and Reports	Number of Measures Evaluated	Results used in this article
Buhaug et al.,(2009)	25	MAC and mitigation potentials for the fleet
EIDE et al. (2011)	25	MAC and mitigation potentials for the fleet
MEPC 62 (2011)	20	Mitigation potentials of an individual measure
HSH Nordbank (2013),	8	Implementation rates of operational and technological measures
Rojon e Smith (2014)	5	Implementation rates of technological measures
DNV GL(2015)	17	Implementation rates of operational and technological measures
IMarEST and Colfax (2015)	24	Implementation rates of operational and technological measures
Lindstad et al. (2015)	12	MAC and mitigation potentials for the fleet
Rehmatulla e Smith (2015a)	9	Implementation rates of operational measures
Rehmatulla et al. (2017b)	30	Implementation rates of technological measures
Bouman et al. (2017)	22	Mitigation potentials of an individual measure
4 th IMO Study (MEPC 75/7/15, 2020)	44	Implementation Rate, MAC and fleet mitigation potentials

The selected measures can have different names depending on the study, although they have the same or similar purposes, or they can yet represent the grouping of several measures used by other studies. The names of the mitigation measures adopted by this article follows the 4th IMO Study (MEPC 75, 2020), in order to reach a broader audience -see Table 2.

Table 2 Name of measures used

Name of the mitigation measures adopted by this article ^a	The 4th IMO study grouping together this measures that are conflicting and that could not be installed on the same ship	For analysis of implementation by Rehmatulla et al. (2015a,2017b), the measures highlighted are the combination of
Speed reduction		general speed reduction, speed reduction due to port efficiency
Voyage optimization		
Hull maintenance	Hull performance monitoring, hull brushing, hull hydro-blasting, dry-dock full blast	
Propeller maintenance	Propeller performance monitoring, propeller polishing	
Super light ship		
Air lubrication		
Hull coating		
Optimization of water flow hull openings		
Hull shape		bulbous bow, aft water line extension, skeg shape and other hull streamlining).
Main engine improvements	Main Engine Tuning, common rail, electronic engine control	common rail and engine tuning
Auxiliary systems		
Propeller improvements	(Propeller-rudder upgrade, propeller upgrade (nozzle, tip winglet), propeller boss cap fins, contra-rotating propeller	weather routing, autopilot adjustment, efficient voyage execution
Reduced auxiliary power demand	(Low energy lighting etc..)	
Waste heat recovery	Waste heat recovery, Exhaust gas boilers on auxiliary engines	
Steam plant improvements		
Hybridization		
Wind power	Towing kite, Wind power (fixed sails or wings), Wind engine (Flettner rotor);	
Solar panels		
Fuel Cells		
Cold ironing		
Zero emission fuel	Hydrogen + ICE or FC, Ammonia + ICE or FC, Synthetic methane + ICE or FC, Biomass methane + ICE or FC, Synthetic methanol + ICE, Biomass methanol + ICE, Synthetic ethanol + ICE, Biomass ethanol + ICE	
Low emission fuel	(LNG+ICE or FC, Methanol + ICE Ethanol + ICE	

^a The characterization of the measures appears in Eide et al. (2009), MEPC 62, (2011), Lindstad et al. (2015) e MEPC 75 (2020).

The organization of these measures into groups also varies among different studies, but two broader groups are consensus among them. The first is the operational mitigation measures, which are measures that change characteristics of the ship's operation, for example, route, speed or maintenance. The measures in this group do not require high capital investments and most of them can be implemented immediately on ships in operation, not requiring them to be

docked. The other group is the technological measures that lead to changes in the ships' systems. In general, they demand moderate to high capital investments and need a docking period for their installation or, in some cases, they can only be installed in new ships. Within the group of technological measures, mitigation measures were grouped into four other subgroups: Hull and Structure, Propulsive System, Auxiliary Power Systems and Alternative Fuels (low or zero emission fuels).

Once the measures to be studied have been defined, it is necessary to assess how the data on mitigation potentials, MACs and implementation rates for each measure should be collected and adjusted. Regarding mitigation potentials, the fleet's mitigation potential was obtained through the MACCs, using four studies - as shown in Table 1. However, to have a single reference value, the results of the 4th IMO study (MEPC 75, 2020) were prioritized, being it the most recent study. When data from this study were lacking, the average of the other existing values was used. For the mitigation potentials of a single measure, which is the potential of the measure installed in a single ship, the mean value found in the review article by Bouman et al. (2017) was used. When this article has no result for the measure in question, the average value of the MEPC 62 report (2011) was used.

For the analysis of the MAC of each mitigation measure, four studies were used. Likewise, to obtain a single reference value, it was prioritized the results of the 4th IMO study (MEPC 75, 2020), and when it does not have a MAC value for the measure in question, the average value of the other studies were used. The most relevant variables in each study used to calculate MACs are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 - Most relevant parameters used by studies that provide MAC data for this article.

Academic Studies and Reports	Discount rate	fuel price	Fleet data used in this article
2nd IMO Study (BUHAUG et al., 2009)	4.00%	HFO: 500 USD/t	all vessels
EIDE et al. (2011)	5.00%	HFO: 350 USD/t; MGO: 450 USD/t	all vessels
Lindstad et al. (2015)	8.00%	HFO: 500 Euros/t - 582 USD/t (nov/2020)	container ships
4 th IMO Study (MEPC 75, 2020)	4.00%	375 USD/t para o HFO (VLSFO)	all vessels

The literature review by Rehmatulla and Smith (2020) reports that there are few studies on the rate of implementation of mitigation measures on ships, citing only four studies: HSH Nordbank (2013), Rojon and Smith (2014), DNV GL (2015), IMarEST and Colfax (2015).

This article considered the studies by Faber et al. (2011), MEPC 75 (2020) were added, in addition to the studies by Rehmatulla and Smith (2015a), Rehmatulla and Smith (2015b), Rehmatulla et al. (2017a), Rehmatulla et al. (2017b) and Rehmatulla and Smith (2020), all

1 referring to the rate of implementation of mitigation measures. For comparison purposes, a
2 single reference value was created consisting of the average between the implementation rates
3 of the 4th IMO study (MEPC 75, 2020) and the corrected compilation of the studies by
4 Rehmatulla and Smith (2015a) and Rehmatulla et al. (2017b)³. Rehmatulla et al. (2017b) assess
5 the pieces of research by HSH Nordbank (2013), Rojon and Smith (2014), DNV GL (2015),
6 IMarEST and Colfax (2015) and consider that they lack methodological rigor. However, for
7 the measures studied in the present work, which had only one of the results — either by
8 Rehmatulla et al. (2015a; 2017b) or from the 4th IMO study — the total average that adds the
9 studies of HSH Nordbank (2013), Rojon and Smith (2014), DNV GL (2015) and IMarEST and
10 Colfax (2015) was used given that the inclusion of other studies decreases the chance of error
11 in the obtained result.
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20 To compare the results of different studies, this article adjusted the implementation rate
21 of Rehmatulla and Smith (2015a) and Rehmatulla et al. (2017b). Rehmatulla and Smith (2015a)
22 interviewed 170 companies; Rehmatulla et al. (2017b) interviewed 200 companies, covering a
23 sample of approximately 5500 ships. These studies calculated the implementation rate from the
24 number of respondents. However, the number of respondents is low for some mitigation
25 measures, resulting in the overestimation of the implementation value (as shown in Table 4).
26 To use an implementation value that could be compatible with other studies, these values were
27 adjusted, considering that non-respondents would not have implemented the measure. Thence,
28 a new result of the percentage of implementation was found, lower than the one informed.
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58 ³The compilation of the studies by Rehmatulla and Smith (2015a) and Rehmatulla et al. (2017b) will be referred
59 in the text as Rehmatulla et al. (2015a; 2017b) to ease the reading.
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Table 4 – Adjusting of the implementation of mitigation measures by Rehmatulla et al. (2015a, 2017b)

Implementation						
Rehmatulla et al. (2015a; 2017b)						
	Implementation ^a	Respondents	Adjusted implementation	4 IMO - MEPC 75 (2020)	Average between Rehmatulla et al. (2015a, 2017b) and 4 IMO	Total mean (with all studies in table 1)
Speed reduction	60.00%*	68.00%	65.00%	0.00% ^b	65.00%	66.00%
Voyage optimization	70.00%*	67.00%	85.00%		85.00%	63.25%
Hull maintenance				50.00%	50.00%	46.00%
Propeller maintenance				12.50%	12.50%	26.25%
Super light ship	50.00%	13.00%	6.50%	0.00%	3.25%	3.25%
Air lubrication	15.00%	9.00%	1.35%	0.00%	0.68%	2.09%
Hull coating				12.50%	12.50%	46.10%
Optimization of water flow hull openings	35.00%	16.00%	5.60%	12.50%	9.05%	9.05%
Hull shape	60.00%*	38.00%	33.75%		16.88%	39.58%
Main engine improvements	40.00%*	45.00%	31.38%	75.00%	53.19%	49.08%
Auxiliary systems	30.00%	44.00%	13.20%	50.00%	31.60%	31.60%
Propeller improvements	25.00%*	93.00%	37.95%	12.50%	25.23%	37.89%
Reduced auxiliary power demand	50.00%	48.00%	24.00%	50.00%	37.00%	33.50%
Waste heat recovery	35.00%	45.00%	15.75%	12.50%	14.13%	14.31%
Steam plant improvements	45.00%	23.00%	10.35%	75.00%	42.68%	42.68%
Hybridization	15.00%	9.00%	1.35%		0.68%	1.35%
Wind power	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Solar panels	3.00%	1.82%	0.05%	0.00%	0.03%	0.03%
Fuel Cells					0.00%	xxx
Cold ironing					0.00%	xxx
Low emission fuels	15.00%	6.00%	0.90%	1.00%	0.95%	1.97%
Zero emission fuels	40.00%	0.18%	0.07%	0.00%	0.04%	0.04%

a - for measures marked with * in this column the rate of implementation of the measure with the highest number of respondents is displayed, but the correction performed in column 4 weighs on all added measures.

b - the percentage of speed reduction presented in the 4th IMO study as the 0% implementation value seems unreal, the explanation given by this article is that it may have been considered by the authors for the construction of the MACC that all ships will reduce the speed beyond what has already been implemented. The values in Table 7 of the other implementation studies attest to the decision to exclude the 0% reduction in speed.

Actually, our findings corroborate the need to adjust the implementation rate by Rehmatulla et al. (2015a; 2017b) when observing the implementation rates of **zero emission fuels** with 40% implementation in Table 7, but with only 0.18% of respondents. When the adjustment is made, the implementation value is reduced to 0.07%. This sharp reduction also occurred in eight other measures, where the number of respondents was less than 20%: **super light ship, air lubrication, optimization of water flow hull openings, hybridization, wind power, solar panels, low emission fuels and zero emission fuels**. The adjusted value always approximates the results of other studies, except for hybridization, which has no other results available. Considering the results of all 17 measures in Rehmatulla et al. (2015a, 2017b), in 13 measures the adjusted result approached the total average, and in four it was distant - showing

that, for measures with a high rate of respondents, the adjusted method may have been rigorous.

Once the data on mitigation potentials, MAC and implementation rates have been collected and treated, it is possible to carry out a comprehensive analysis of the implementation rates, which includes the comparison of implementation in negative and positive MAC measures, and identifying the implementation rate of measures that have the most significant potential for mitigation. This is the focus of the next section of this study.

4. Results

Firstly, the compilation of the mitigation potential of abatement measures are compiled in Table 5.

Table 5 Compilation of mitigation potential of operational and technological measures

Mitigation Potential							
Mitigation Measures	Mitigation potential for the fleet						Mitigation potential for individual measure
	2020 2 IMO - Buhaug et al. (2009)	2030 - Eide et al. (2011)	2030 - Lindstad et al. (2015)	2030 4 IMO - MEPC 75 (2020)	2050 4 IMO - MEPC 75 (2020)	Reference value for the fleet	Bouman et al. (2017) and MEPC 62 (2011)
Speed reduction	8.00%	9.15%	2.00%	7.38%	7.54%	7.54%	20.00%
Voyage optimization	2.00%	2.29%	5.00%			3.64%	8.00%
Hull maintenance	1.60%	1.96%		2.22%	3.90%	3.90%	5.00%
Propeller maintenance	3.60%	0.65%		2.20%	3.95%	3.95%	5.50%
Super light ship				0.28%	0.39%	0.39%	5.00%
Air lubrication	1.60%	3.92%		1.35%	2.26%	2.26%	5.00%
Hull coating	1.60%			1.48%	2.55%	2.55%	5.00%
Optimization of water flow hull openings	2.40%			1.64%	3.00%	3.00%	3.00%
Hull shape			8.00%			8.00%	15.00%
Main engine improvements	0.40%	1.31%		0.25%	0.45%	0.45%	0.50%
Auxiliary systems	0.20%	3.27%		0.87%	1.59%	1.59%	0.60%
Propeller improvements	4.00%	5.88%	4.00%	1.40%	2.40%	2.40%	5.00%
Reduced auxiliary power demand	0.20%	0.46%	2.00%	0.40%	0.71%	0.71%	2.00%
Waste heat recovery		5.88%	3.00%	1.68%	3.09%	3.09%	9.00%
Steam plant improvements		0.65%		1.30%	2.13%	2.13%	xxxx
Hybridization			4.00%			4.00%	5.00%
Wind power	5.60%	5.23%		0.89%	0.89%	1.66%	13.00%
Solar panels				0.18%	0.30%	0.30%	5.00%
Fuel Cells		1.63%				1.63%	7.00%
Cold ironing		1.31%				1.31%	6.00%
Low emission fuels				5.54%	0.00%	1.85%	20.00%
Zero emission fuels				0.10%	64.08%	64.08%	70.00%

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As noted, **zero emission fuels** have the highest mitigation potential value for a single measure (70%), and also the highest potential in the fleet reference value (64%), a result highlighted in 4th IMO study (MEPC 75, 2020). Therefore, in terms of mitigation potential, this measure has the most significant impact in both analyses. The second measure with the most significant mitigation potential in the fleet in the 2050 reference value is **the hull shape**, which appears as the third most significant potential in a single measure in Bouman et al. (2017). The third greatest potential measure for the fleet at the reference value is **speed reduction**, second in Bouman et al. (2017). It is noteworthy that these last two measures mentioned were already commented on in the analyses of the evolution of emissions in maritime transport (see Section 1). There, they were identified as responsible for the drop in emissions from 2008 to 2012, and for the increase in the efficiency of vessels. In line with this analysis, these measures should have a high percentage of implementation. Despite appearing in Bouman et al. (2017) as the fourth-highest percentage mitigation measure in the 4th IMO study (MEPC 75, 2020), the wind power mitigation measure has only 1.66% fleet mitigation potential. This study does not comment on these results. However, it is assumed that the low mitigation value must refer to the low percentage of the fleet that can be installed, since MEPC 62 (2011) does not consider the installation of **wind power** to be feasible (*kites* or *Flettner rotor*) in container ships; in addition, SMITH et al. (2014) show some scenarios in which this class of ships can occupy up to $\frac{2}{3}$ of world ship emissions in 2050. In Bouman et al. (2017), **low emission fuels** appear as the second measure with most significant potential for mitigation, along with **speed reduction**, with 20% emission reduction potential. However, this value does not consider the methane slip and is therefore optimistic.

Having observed the mitigation potentials, then the compiled abatement costs of each measure is presented in Table 6.

Table 6 - Compilation of MAC values (US\$/tCO₂)

MACs						
	2 IMO - Buhaug et al. (2009) (US\$/tCO ₂)	Eide et al. (2011) (US\$/tCO ₂)	Lindstad et al. (2015) (US\$/tCO ₂ eq) ^a	4 IMO - MEPC 75 (2020) (US\$/tCO ₂)	Mean (US\$/tCO ₂)	Reference value (US\$/tCO ₂)
Speed reduction	110	80	0	10	67	10
Voyage optimization	-150	-90	-135		-120	-120
Hull maintenance	-105	-30		-91	-75	-91
Propeller maintenance	-75	-50		-102	-76	-102
Super light ship				54	54	54
Air lubrication	-130	-30		93	-22	93
Hull coating	-105			-50	-78	-50
Optimization of water flow hull openings	-155			-119	-137	-119
Hull shape			-73		-73	-73
Main engine improvements	-44	-80		-34	-53	-34
Auxiliary systems	80	-50		-39	-3	-39
Propeller improvements	-115	-70	-73	18	-56	18
Reduced auxiliary power demand	80	-80	-98	-59	-20	-59
Waste heat recovery			306	54	54	54
Steam plant improvements		-90		-111	-101	-111
Hybridization			86		86	86
Wind power	-110	0		2	-36	2
Solar panels		1000		1048	1024	1048
Fuel Cells		60			60	60
Cold ironing		200			200	200
Low emission fuels				249	249	249
Zero emission fuels				416	416	416

^a Values provided were in euros/tCO₂eq and were converted to US\$/tCO₂eq based on the May/2021 dollar rate. CO₂eq uses GWP100 equivalence.

Among the 22 measures analyzed, in five measures the MAC value alternates between positive and negative: **auxiliary systems, reduced auxiliary power demand, propeller improvements, wind power and air lubrication**. However, between the average and the reference value, only two measures oscillate between positive and negative: for the **air lubrication** measurement, as it has a low implementation rate (to be seen in Table 7), this suggests that the positive MAC result in a reasonable value. For the measure of **propeller improvements**, its positive MAC, according to the 4th IMO study (MEPC 75, 2020) is contradictory with the high implementation of the measure (which can also be seen in Table 7). Although the MAC value of the **propeller improvements** is positive, its cost is low (18 USD/tCO₂), and as this value is an average for the entire fleet, an explanation for its relatively high implementation rate could be that a percentage of the fleet have a negative MAC for that measure. However, another explanation could be given by observing Table 6, where the only study that defines this MAC as positive is the 4th IMO study (MEPC 75, 2020), thus indicating

that the MAC value used as a reference may be overestimated. In the other measures that oscillate between positive and negative, in the case of **reduced auxiliary power demand** and **auxiliary systems**, this oscillation is carried out only by the result of the 2nd IMO study (BUHAUG et al., 2009), which is the oldest one. Finally, **wind power**, whose positive values are very close to zero, points to a trend towards a negative value. This analysis of the oscillation between positive and negative results of MACs listed in Table 6 indicates that, qualitatively, there is a convergence on which measures are positive or negative.

After observing the MAC values, the results of the implementations are presented.

Table 7 - Compilation of implementation rates

	Implementation						Average between Rehmttulla et al.(2015a, 2017b) e 4 th IMO	Total mean	Reference value
	HSH Nordbank (2013) ^b	Rojon e Smith (2014)	IMarEST and Colfax (2015)	DNV GL(2015)	Rehmttulla et al. (2015a; 2017b) adjusted	4 th IMO - MEPC 75 (2020)			
Speed reduction	85%		35%	79%	65%	0%	65%	66%	66%
Voyage optimization	67%		33%	68%	85%		85%	63%	63%
Hull maintenance			42%			50%	50%	46%	46%
Propeller maintenance			40%	85%^a		13%	13%	26%	26%
Super light ship					7%	0%	3%	3%	3%
Air lubrication	2%		5%		1%	0%	1%	2%	1%
Hull coating	38%	70%	37%	73%		13%	13%	46%	46%
Optimization of water flow hull openings					6%	13%	9%	9%	9%
Hull shape	62%			23%^c	34%		34%	40%	40%
Main engine improvements		58%	22%	59%	31%	75%	53%	49%	53%
Auxiliary systems					13%	50%	32%	32%	32%
Propeller improvements	53%	55%		31%	38%	13%	25%	38%	25%
Reduced auxiliary power demand			25%	35%	24%	50%	37%	34%	37%
Waste heat recovery	7%		22%		16%	13%	14%	14%	14%
Steam plant improvements					10%	75%	43%	43%	43%
Hybridization					1%		1%	1%	1%
Wind power					0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Solar panels					0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Fuel Cells							0%	xxx	
Cold ironing			19%				0%	xxx	
Low emission fuels	4%				1%	1%	1%	2%	1%
Zero emission fuels			18%^a		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

a Alternative fuel measures in IMarest and Colfax (2015) and hull and thruster cleaning in DNV GL (2015) were not included in the sum as the value is consolidated, but was displayed in the table to enrich the observation

b Measures in bold in HSH NORDBANK (2013) are information from operators who plan to implement the measure.

c The hull shape measurement in DNV GL (2015) refers to the retrofitting implementation of hull changes. Therefore, the value that includes new ships tends to be higher.

From the 22 measures analyzed, two measures do not have implementation results, seven have less than 5% implementation, one measure has between 5 and 10% implementation, five have between 10 and 40% and seven have more than 40% implementation. **Fuel cell** and **cold-ironing** measures were not evaluated as they are not included in the results of Rehmatulla et al. (2015a; 2017b) or in the MPEC 75 report (2020). The **cold ironing** measure was rated at 19% implementation in the DNV GL (2015) report. The **fuel cell** implementation rate does not appear in any of the studies referred to in this article.

For better visualization of implementation rates, they are displayed in a *box plot* graph (see Figure 3), including HSH Nordbank (2013) surveys; Rojon and Smith (2014); DNV GL (2015); IMarEST and Colfax (2015); Rehmatulla and Smith (2015a); Rehmatulla et al. (2017b); MEPC 75 (2020). The measures are presented according to the reference value of MACs, from the top (lowest value) to the bottom (highest value).

Figure 3 - Box plot of the implementation of measures sorted by MAC value

To wrap up the analyses, we bring together the three results: mitigation potential, MAC and implementation rate (see Table 8).

Table 8 Compilation of Mitigation Potential, MAC and Implementation Rate results for mitigation measures

Mitigation Measure	Mitigation Potential		MAC	Implementation
	Reference value - for the fleet	Bouman et al. (2017) e MEPC 62 (2011) for an individual measure	MAC reference value	Implementation rate reference value
Speed reduction	8%	20%	10	66%
Voyage optimization	4%	8%	-120	63%
Hull maintenance	4%	5%	-91	46%
Propeller maintenance	4%	6%	-102	26%
Super light ship	0%	5%	54	3%
Air lubrication	2%	5%	93	1%
Hull coating	3%	5%	-50	46%
Optimization of water flow hull openings	3%	3%	-119	9%
Hull shape	8%	15%	-60	40%
Main engine improvements	0%	1%	-34	53%
Auxiliary systems	2%	1%	-39	32%
Propeller improvements	2%	5%	18	25%
Reduced auxiliary power demand	1%	2%	-59	37%
Waste heat recovery	3%	9%	54	14%
Steam plant improvements	2%	xxxxx	-111	43%
Hybridization	4%	5%	70	1%
Wind power	2%	13%	2	0%
Solar panels	0%	5%	1.048	0%
Fuel Cells	2%	7%	60	xxxxx
Cold ironing	1%	6%	200	xxxxx
Low emission fuels	2%	20%	249	1%
Zero emission fuels	64%	70%	416	0%

Positive and negative MAC measures were compared in relation to their implementation rates. From the 22 measures analyzed, 10 had negative MAC and 12 had positive MAC – of the latter, only implementation data of 10 measures were used, since **cold ironing** and **fuel cell** data were not used.

Among measures with negative MAC, 27% (3 measures) had more than 50% implementation by the market, and 90% (9 measures) had more than 25% implementation - these percentages are not so high as expected for measures with negative MAC. However, it is worth considering that heterogeneity prevents many measures from reaching 100%

1 implementation⁴. Among the measures with positive MAC, only the **speed reduction** had more
2 than 50% implementation; and 20% (2 measures) have more than 25% implementation, **speed**
3 **reduction** and **propeller improvements**; only 1 measure is between 5% and 25% of
4 implementation: **waste heat recovery**. Also, among the positive MAC measures, 70% have
5 less than 5% implementation.
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9 It is worth investigating the reasons why three positive MAC measures have more than
10 5% implementation. The speed reduction measure, although it has a positive MAC, has
11 economic advantages when implemented, as it reduces fuel costs. Its positive cost is related to
12 acquiring new ships to maintain the freight tonnage performed before the measure is
13 implemented. However, companies do not always operate by acquiring new ships because
14 when the market is down, it generates a surplus of ships and, therefore, the **speed reduction**
15 balances this offer in the market (PSARAFTIS and KANTOVAS, 2013). Faber et al. (2011)
16 comment that none of the four companies interviewed in their study increased their fleet to
17 compensate for the speed reduction, which may explain their high implementation. The second
18 measure to be commented on is the **propeller improvement**, which only has MAC assessed
19 as positive by the 4th IMO study (MEPC 75.2020). In the other studies all MAC values are
20 negative and, as mentioned, the reference value may be overestimated, which may explain the
21 high implementation.
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24 The third measure with positive MAC with an implementation greater than 5% is **waste**
25 **heat recovery**, which has an implementation rate of 14%. The justification for this could be
26 heterogeneity, as the MAC value must vary according to the size of the fleet or the class of
27 ship. Eide et al. (2009), for example, has negative values for the MAC of this measure for
28 containers and positive for bulk carriers. However, in Lindstad et al. (2015), which
29 differentiates the MACs by class of ship, the measure had a positive MAC for all classes, except
30 for tankers. This was because the work understands that the waste heat in these ships is used
31 for steam production and not for electricity production, so the oil tankers would not implement
32 this mitigation measure. This differentiation shows a common mistake with the analysis of this
33 measure, as the understanding of what composes the measure is different between authors,
34 leading to different costs. For example, Wang and Lutsey (2013) assigned a MAC value of
35 approximately USD 10/t CO₂ to the measure, but they use the name of waste heat *reduction*, a
36 different designation from the one adopted here. In Rehmatulla et al. (2017b), of the ships that
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58 ⁴The MEPC 62 (2011) report describes which ship classes and which sizes could not install certain mitigation
59 measures.
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1 implemented the measure, 45% are oil tankers, 30% bulk carriers, 20% containers and 5% other
2 classes, in a universe of 2500 respondent ships, which shows a predominance of installation in
3 the oil tanker fleet – despite using the term waste heat *recovery*. It can be inferred that the
4 regular implementation of a measure with a high MAC by the market may be motivated by
5 fleet heterogeneity or by hidden cost problems since the assignment of a high MAC value to
6 this measure must be linked to an understanding of application that excludes oil tankers.
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10 From the measures with negative MAC, only the **optimization of water flow hull**
11 **openings** has less than 10% implementation (8%) and needs further studies to assess its reason.
12 However, it is worth noting that the ICCT (2011) work mentions that this measure is already
13 highly implemented by the market, but without presenting the values.
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18 To sum up, our results show a clear relation between the implementation of measures
19 and whether their MACs are negative or positive, as negative MAC measures have a good
20 implementation, and positive MAC measures have a low implementation (which is also
21 observed in Figure 3). It is noteworthy that 90% of negative MAC measures have more than
22 25% implementation, 80% of measures more than 30%, 60% of measures with more than 40%
23 and 30% more than 50% implementation. Therefore, negative MAC measures are promising
24 concerning implementation rates and, therefore, these implementation data should be
25 considered in scenario studies that build estimates for 2050. However, there is still room for
26 lowering market failures and increasing the implementation of win-win measures.
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34 On the contrary, among the measures with the highest GHG emission mitigation
35 potential for the fleet and for a single measure, the only measure with a low implementation
36 rate is **associated with alternative fuels (low emission and zero emission fuels)**. Considering
37 the average 30-year service life of ships, it is critical to encourage new ships to implement this
38 technological measure with a high MAC value, as this measure will require regulation for its
39 implementation (LLOYDS and UMAS, 2020). Furthermore, the EEDI policy will not be able
40 to encourage it, due to the high MAC, already mentioned, and since EEDI also does not yet
41 incorporate zero emission fuel reductions.
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50 **Conclusion and Policy Implications**

51 This study observed that the market effectively implements measures with negative
52 MACs more than those with positive MACs. Negative MAC measures have more than 25%
53 implementation, with only one exception. Although the mitigation potential of negative MAC
54 measures is now reduced, as part of the fleet already have implemented these measures, there
55 is still opportunities to implement win-win measures, addressing market failures, such as lack
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1 of access to capital, information asymmetries and split costs (contract problems). The
2 implementation rate should be taken into account when estimating emission scenarios for 2050.

3
4 Among the measures with the most significant mitigation potential, three stand out:
5 **zero emission fuels, hull shape, and speed reduction.** From these measures, **zero emission**
6 **fuel** is the one with the most significant mitigation potential, with null or almost null
7 implementation as of today. Therefore, it is difficult to design a policy with a high and quick
8 impact on reducing GHG emissions that does not include zero emission fuels, since the other
9 two measures with high mitigation potential are already well implemented by the market and
10 should not be installed again in a relevant fraction of the fleet. Policies to boost the
11 implementation of zero emission fuels are critical to reduce GHG emissions. They should be
12 divided into policies that address the existing fleet, where the focus should be on retrofit (this
13 include alternative drop-in fuels mandates, e.g.); and policies that address new ships where
14 different powertrains may be tested being based on non-drop-in fuels such as ammonia.
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Table 1 Studies from where the data was taken to compose the results of the next chapter.

Academic Studies and Reports	Number of Measures Evaluated	Results used in this article
Buhaug et al.,(2009)	25	MAC and mitigation potentials for the fleet
EIDE et al. (2011)	25	MAC and mitigation potentials for the fleet
MEPC 62 (2011)	20	Mitigation potentials of an individual measure
HSH Nordbank (2013),	8	Implementation rates of operational and technological measures
Rojon e Smith (2014)	5	Implementation rates of technological measures
DNV GL(2015)	17	Implementation rates of operational and technological measures
IMarEST and Colfax (2015)	24	Implementation rates of operational and technological measures
Lindstad et al. (2015)	12	MAC and mitigation potentials for the fleet
Rehmatulla e Smith (2015a)	9	Implementation rates of operational measures
Rehmatulla et al. (2017b)	30	Implementation rates of technological measures
Bouman et al. (2017)	22	Mitigation potentials of an individual measure
4 th IMO Study (MEPC 75/7/15, 2020)	44	Implementation Rate, MAC and fleet mitigation potentials

Table 2 Name of measures used

Name of the mitigation measures adopted by this article ^a	The 4th IMO study grouping together this measures that are conflicting and that could not be installed on the same ship	For analysis of implementation by Rehmatulla et al. (2015a,2017b), the measures highlighted are the combination of
Speed reduction		general speed reduction, speed reduction due to port efficiency
Voyage optimization		
Hull maintenance	Hull performance monitoring, hull brushing, hull hydro-blasting, dry-dock full blast	
Propeller maintenance	Propeller performance monitoring, propeller polishing	
Super light ship		
Air lubrication		
Hull coating		
Optimization of water flow hull openings		
Hull shape		bulbous bow, aft water line extension, skeg shape and other hull streamlining).
Main engine improvements	Main Engine Tuning, common rail, electronic engine control	common rail and engine tuning
Auxiliary systems		
Propeller improvements	(Propeller-rudder upgrade, propeller upgrade (nozzle, tip winglet), propeller boss cap fins, contra-rotating propeller	weather routing, autopilot adjustment, efficient voyage execution
Reduced auxiliary power demand	(Low energy lighting etc..)	
Waste heat recovery	Waste heat recovery, Exhaust gas boilers on auxiliary engines	
Steam plant improvements		
Hybridization		

Wind power	Towing kite, Wind power (fixed sails or wings), Wind engine (Flettner rotor);
Solar panels	
Fuel Cells	
Cold ironing	
Zero emission fuel	Hydrogen + ICE or FC, Ammonia + ICE or FC, Synthetic methane + ICE or FC, Biomass methane + ICE or FC, Synthetic methanol + ICE, Biomass methanol + ICE, Synthetic ethanol + ICE, Biomass ethanol + ICE
Low emission fuel	(LNG+ICE or FC, Methanol + ICE Ethanol + ICE

a The characterization of the measures appears in Eide et al. (2009), MEPC 62, (2011), Lindstad et al. (2015) e MEPC 75 (2020).

Table 3 - Most relevant parameters used by studies that provide MAC data for this article.

Academic Studies and Reports	Discount rate	fuel price	Fleet data used in this article
2nd IMO Study (BUHAUG et al., 2009)	4.00%	HFO: 500 USD/t	all vessels
EIDE et al. (2011)	5.00%	HFO: 350 USD/t; MGO: 450 USD/t	all vessels
Lindstad et al. (2015)	8.00%	HFO: 500 Euros/t - 582 USD/t (nov/2020)	container ships
4 th IMO Study (MEPC 75, 2020)	4.00%	375 USD/t para o HFO (VLSFO)	all vessels

Table 4 – Adjusting of the implementation of mitigation measures by Rehmatulla et al. (2015a, 2017b)

	Implementation					
	Implementation ^a	Respondents	Adjusted implementation	4 IMO - MEPC 75 (2020)	Average between Rehmatulla et al. (2015a, 2017b) and 4 IMO	Total mean (with all studies in table 1)
Speed reduction	60.00%*	68.00%	65.00%	0.00% ^b	65.00%	66.00%
Voyage optimization	70.00%*	67.00%	85.00%		85.00%	63.25%
Hull maintenance				50.00%	50.00%	46.00%
Propeller maintenance				12.50%	12.50%	26.25%
Super light ship	50.00%	13.00%	6.50%	0.00%	3.25%	3.25%
Air lubrication	15.00%	9.00%	1.35%	0.00%	0.68%	2.09%
Hull coating				12.50%	12.50%	46.10%
Optimization of water flow hull openings	35.00%	16.00%	5.60%	12.50%	9.05%	9.05%
Hull shape	60.00%*	38.00%	33.75%		16.88%	39.58%
Main engine improvements	40.00%*	45.00%	31.38%	75.00%	53.19%	49.08%
Auxiliary systems	30.00%	44.00%	13.20%	50.00%	31.60%	31.60%
Propeller improvements	25.00%*	93.00%	37.95%	12.50%	25.23%	37.89%
Reduced auxiliary power demand	50.00%	48.00%	24.00%	50.00%	37.00%	33.50%
Waste heat recovery	35.00%	45.00%	15.75%	12.50%	14.13%	14.31%
Steam plant improvements	45.00%	23.00%	10.35%	75.00%	42.68%	42.68%

Hybridization	15.00%	9.00%	1.35%		0.68%	1.35%
Wind power	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Solar panels	3.00%	1.82%	0.05%	0.00%	0.03%	0.03%
Fuel Cells					0.00%	xxx
Cold ironing					0.00%	xxx
Low emission fuels	15.00%	6.00%	0.90%	1.00%	0.95%	1.97%
Zero emission fuels	40.00%	0.18%	0.07%	0.00%	0.04%	0.04%

a - for measures marked with * in this column the rate of implementation of the measure with the highest number of respondents is displayed, but the correction performed in column 4 weighs on all added measures.

b - the percentage of speed reduction presented in the 4th IMO study as the 0% implementation value seems unreal, the explanation given by this article is that it may have been considered by the authors for the construction of the MACC that all ships will reduce the speed beyond what has already been implemented. The values in Table 7 of the other implementation studies attest to the decision to exclude the 0% reduction in speed.

Table 5 Compilation of mitigation potential of operational and technological measures

Mitigation Measures	Mitigation Potential						Mitigation potential for individual measure
	Mitigation potential for the fleet						
	2020 2 IMO - Buhaug et al. (2009)	2030 - Eide et al. (2011)	2030 - Lindstad et al. (2015)	2030 4 IMO - MEPC 75 (2020)	2050 4 IMO - MEPC 75 (2020)	Reference value for the fleet	Bouman et al. (2017) and MEPC 62 (2011)
Speed reduction	8.00%	9.15%	2.00%	7.38%	7.54%	7.54%	20.00%
Voyage optimization	2.00%	2.29%	5.00%			3.64%	8.00%
Hull maintenance	1.60%	1.96%		2.22%	3.90%	3.90%	5.00%
Propeller maintenance	3.60%	0.65%		2.20%	3.95%	3.95%	5.50%
Super light ship				0.28%	0.39%	0.39%	5.00%
Air lubrication	1.60%	3.92%		1.35%	2.26%	2.26%	5.00%
Hull coating	1.60%			1.48%	2.55%	2.55%	5.00%
Optimization of water flow hull openings	2.40%			1.64%	3.00%	3.00%	3.00%
Hull shape			8.00%			8.00%	15.00%
Main engine improvements	0.40%	1.31%		0.25%	0.45%	0.45%	0.50%
Auxiliary systems	0.20%	3.27%		0.87%	1.59%	1.59%	0.60%
Propeller improvements	4.00%	5.88%	4.00%	1.40%	2.40%	2.40%	5.00%
Reduced auxiliary power demand	0.20%	0.46%	2.00%	0.40%	0.71%	0.71%	2.00%
Waste heat recovery		5.88%	3.00%	1.68%	3.09%	3.09%	9.00%
Steam plant improvements		0.65%		1.30%	2.13%	2.13%	xxxx
Hybridization			4.00%			4.00%	5.00%
Wind power	5.60%	5.23%		0.89%	0.89%	1.66%	13.00%
Solar panels				0.18%	0.30%	0.30%	5.00%
Fuel Cells		1.63%				1.63%	7.00%
Cold ironing		1.31%				1.31%	6.00%
Low emission fuels				5.54%	0.00%	1.85%	20.00%
Zero emission fuels				0.10%	64.08%	64.08%	70.00%

Table 6 - Compilation of MAC values (US\$/tCO₂)

MACs

	2 IMO - Buhaug et al. (2009) (US\$/tCO2)	Eide et al. (2011) (US\$/tCO2)	Lindstad et al. (2015) (US\$/tCO2eq) ^a	4 IMO - MEPC 75 (2020) (US\$/tCO2)	Mean (US\$/tCO2)	Reference value (US\$/tCO2)
Speed reduction	110	80	0	10	67	10
Voyage optimization	-150	-90	-135		-120	-120
Hull maintenance	-105	-30		-91	-75	-91
Propeller maintenance	-75	-50		-102	-76	-102
Super light ship				54	54	54
Air lubrication	-130	-30		93	-22	93
Hull coating	-105			-50	-78	-50
Optimization of water flow hull openings	-155			-119	-137	-119
Hull shape			-73		-73	-73
Main engine improvements	-44	-80		-34	-53	-34
Auxiliary systems	80	-50		-39	-3	-39
Propeller improvements	-115	-70	-73	18	-56	18
Reduced auxiliary power demand	80	-80	-98	-59	-20	-59
Waste heat recovery			306	54	54	54
Steam plant improvements		-90		-111	-101	-111
Hybridization			86		86	86
Wind power	-110	0		2	-36	2
Solar panels		1000		1048	1024	1048
Fuel Cells		60			60	60
Cold ironing		200			200	200
Low emission fuels				249	249	249
Zero emission fuels				416	416	416

a Values provided were in euros/tCO2eq and were converted to US\$/tCO2eq based on the May/2021 dollar rate. CO2eq uses GWP100 equivalence.

Table 7 - Compilation of implementation rates

	Implementation						Avarage between Rehmattula et al.(2015a, 2017b) e 4 th IMO	Total mean	Reference value
	HSH Nordbank (2013) ^b	Rojon e Smith (2014)	IMarEST and Colfax (2015)	DNV GL(2015)	Rehmattula et al. (2015a; 2017b) adjusted	4 th IMO - MEPC 75 (2020)			
Speed reduction	85%		35%	79%	65%	0%	65%	66%	66%
Voyage optimization	67%		33%	68%	85%		85%	63%	63%
Hull maintenance			42%			50%	50%	46%	46%
Propeller maintenance			40%	85%^a		13%	13%	26%	26%
Super light ship					7%	0%	3%	3%	3%
Air lubrication	2%		5%		1%	0%	1%	2%	1%
Hull coating	38%	70%	37%	73%		13%	13%	46%	46%
Optimization of water flow hull openings					6%	13%	9%	9%	9%
Hull shape	62%			23%^c	34%		34%	40%	40%
Main engine improvements		58%	22%	59%	31%	75%	53%	49%	53%
Auxiliary systems					13%	50%	32%	32%	32%
Propeller improvements	53%	55%		31%	38%	13%	25%	38%	25%
Reduced auxiliary power demand			25%	35%	24%	50%	37%	34%	37%

Waste heat recovery	7%	22%	16%	13%	14%	14%	14%
Steam plant improvements			10%	75%	43%	43%	43%
Hybridization			1%		1%	1%	1%
Wind power			0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Solar panels			0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Fuel Cells					0%	xxx	
Cold ironing		19%			0%	xxx	
Low emission fuels	4%		1%	1%	1%	2%	1%
Zero emission fuels		18%^a	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

a Alternative fuel measures in IMarest and Colfax (2015) and hull and thruster cleaning in DNV GL (2015) were not included in the sum as the value is consolidated, but was displayed in the table to enrich the observation

b Measures in bold in HSH NORDBANK (2013) are information from operators who plan to implement the measure.

c The hull shape measurement in DNV GL (2015) refers to the retrofitting implementation of hull changes. Therefore, the value that includes new ships tends to be higher.

Table 8 Compilation of Mitigation Potential, MAC and Implementation Rate results for mitigation measures

Mitigation Measure	Mitigation Potential		MAC	Implementation
	Reference value - for the fleet	Bouman et al. (2017) e MEPC 62 (2011) for an individual measure	MAC reference value	Implementation rate reference value
Speed reduction	8%	20%	10	66%
Voyage optimization	4%	8%	-120	63%
Hull maintenance	4%	5%	-91	46%
Propeller maintenance	4%	6%	-102	26%
Super light ship	0%	5%	54	3%
Air lubrication	2%	5%	93	1%
Hull coating	3%	5%	-50	46%
Optimization of water flow hull openings	3%	3%	-119	9%
Hull shape	8%	15%	-60	40%
Main engine improvements	0%	1%	-34	53%
Auxiliary systems	2%	1%	-39	32%
Propeller improvements	2%	5%	18	25%
Reduced auxiliary power demand	1%	2%	-59	37%
Waste heat recovery	3%	9%	54	14%
Steam plant improvements	2%	xxxxx	-111	43%
Hybridization	4%	5%	70	1%
Wind power	2%	13%	2	0%
Solar panels	0%	5%	1.048	0%
Fuel Cells	2%	7%	60	xxxxx
Cold ironing	1%	6%	200	xxxxx
Low emission fuels	2%	20%	249	1%
Zero emission fuels	64%	70%	416	0%